

Discriminating Interactions of Chiral Metal Complexes

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IN 1943, Professor P. Rây and his collaborator Dr. N. K. Dutt, while studying the kinetics and mechanism of the racemisation of (+) and (-) $[\text{Co}(\text{biguanide})_3]^{3+}$, discovered that the rate of racemisation of the (+) complex, in the presence of a second chiral species, namely tartrate⁻, was different from that of the (-) complex in the same chiral environment. In other words, the (+) tartrate⁻ in its interaction with the oppositely charged metal complex discriminated between its (+) and (-) forms. It seems appropriate, on this occasion, to trace some of the subsequent developments in the area of this discovery.

That there is a difference in the interaction of enantiomeric molecules (*d, l*)^{*} with a second chiral molecule which may be the same species or a different species (*D, L*) was first discovered by Pasteur² who used it to resolve racemates. Discriminating interactions may be represented schematically as :

- (a) the difference between the interactions

- (b) the difference between the interactions

In order to describe that part of the interaction between chiral molecules which discriminates between like (*l-l*) and unlike pairs (*l-d*), Craig and Mellor³ have introduced the term chirodiastaltic (chiro = hand, diastaltic = serving to distinguish between). A chirodiastaltic interaction is a special kind of stereospecific interaction which occurs among assemblies of molecules of different chirality.

The subject has already been treated in some detail, especially in its theoretical aspects³. Consequently this brief review will be limited to chirodiastaltic interactions of metal complexes—mainly of the kinds studied by Ray and Dutt.

Interest in such interactions was increased by the work of Dwyer and his collaborators who described discriminatory phenomena in terms of the concept of 'configurational activity'⁴†. They showed, for example that

(1) the solubilities of the (+) and (-) forms of $[\text{Ru}(o\text{-phen})_3] (\text{ClO}_4)_2$ in solutions of (+) tartrate⁻ were different.

(2) the oxidation reduction potentials of the system⁵ :

were differently affected by the addition of another chiral ion such as (+) bromo-camphorsulphonate⁻.

(3) the rates of racemisation of (+) and (-) $[\text{Ni}(o\text{-phen})_3]\text{Cl}_2$ were different in the presence of (+) bromo-camphorsulphonate⁻ thus confirming the earlier observation of Ray and Dutt.

Theoretical studies⁷ of chirodiastaltic interactions between molecules (or ions) locked in fixed, average, relative orientations, support the conclusion that the whole of configurational activity can be attributed to the influence of diastereoisomers in solution⁸.

Doubts about the adequacy of this explanation were raised when Dwyer and Davies reported that the rate of racemisation of (+) and (-) $[\text{Ni}(o\text{-phen})_3]^{2+}$ (*d*⁺) differed in the presence of a cationic species namely (+) cinchoninium H⁺ ion (*D*⁺)⁹. This seemed irreconcilable with the concept of locked up diastereoisomeric ion-pairs in solution. Chirodiastaltic interactions between ionic species of the same charge are not confined to the process of racemisation. They have been found in oxidation reduction systems⁵ and systems showing the Pfeiffer effect[≠]. The two situations may be represented schematically :

* Note on symbols : The letters *d l* represent enantiomeric molecules, *d⁺ l⁺* enantiomeric ions ; the lines connecting these symbols represent an interaction of whatever kind. Dextro and levo rotations are represented by (+) and (-) respectively, placed before the names of the compounds concerned.

† The activity coefficient of a chiral ion in the presence of chiral ion of a different species includes a factor dependent on the configuration of the second species.

≠ This refers to the anomalous change in optical rotation produced when a substance like (+) bromocamphorsulphonate is added to, for example, a solution of racemic $[\text{Zn}(o\text{-phen})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$.

Since the magnitude of the observed effects produced by both kinds of interaction (i) and (ii) is about the same³, it is reasonable to assume that the same mechanism is involved in each case. An alternative explanation, applicable to both (i) and (ii), is that the discriminatory interactions arise from long range forces of electrical origin. If long range interactions are involved, they can be responsible for the experimental observations only if the molecules are in fixed relative orientations for a sufficiently long time; otherwise, that is with freely rotating molecules or ions, the long range contribution to discrimination is too small to account for the observed magnitudes. A crucial question is: by what mechanism are the molecules constrained to fixed relative orientations? There is at present no clear cut answer. Evidence supporting hypothesis of long range interactions has been reviewed by Schipper⁸.

However, Miyoshi *et al*⁹ have recently suggested a mechanism by which contact interaction could occur in both systems (i) and (ii). They have drawn an analogy between the behaviour of ionised surfactant molecules and that of metal complexes of the kind being considered in this review. At a concentration known as the 'critical micelle concentration' surfactant molecules (cationic or anionic) form aggregates despite their electrostatic repulsions. This phenomenon has been interpreted in terms of hydrophobic bonding between the hydrophobic parts of the surfactant ions. Their proposal is that, in a similar manner, ions like (+)-[Ni(o-phen)₃]²⁺ make contact with the (+) cinchonine H⁺ through hydrophobic bonding despite their electrostatic repulsion. This process is said to be enhanced by the presence of some species of achiral anions—presumably, through the formation of triple ions. Miyoshi *et al* have found evidence for hydrophobic bonding in their observations on the Pfeiffer effect produced by adding (-) strychnine H⁺ to heavy water solutions of [Zn(o-phen)₃]SO₄.

Both explanations of the nature of the chiral interactions in (i) and (ii) — namely that involving the operation of long range forces, electrical in origin,

and that involving contact interactions seem equally plausible: there does not appear to be any really compelling evidence favoring one or the other. Clearly, further experiments are necessary.

There have been occasions when, instead of the customary organic acids and bases, chiral metal complexes themselves have been used in the resolution of racemic metal complexes. For example, Dwyer *et al*¹⁰ used (+) [Co(en)₃]³⁺ to resolve (±) [Co(EDTA)]₃. In solutions of (+) [(Co(en)₃)] (+) [Co(EDTA)]₃ or similar diastereoisomers where even heavier metal atom are present, it might be possible to measure metal atom to metal atom distances by means of x-ray diffraction and so establish the existence or otherwise of locked ion-pairs.

References

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